

A Study on the Contemporary Socio-Economic and Educational Problems of Child Labour in Kolkata

Alik Kumar Mondal¹ and Goutam Bandyopadhyay²

¹M.Phil. Scholar, Ramakrishna Mission Sikshanamandira, Belur Math, Howrah, W.B.
E-mail – akm.alik999@gmail.com

²Associate Professor, Ramakrishna Mission Sikshanamandira,
Belur Math, Howrah, W.B.

ABSTRACT : Child labour refers to children who miss their childhood and are not able to have the basic amenities which a child should have. The problem of child labour is huge and is faced by many countries in the world. In India many children who belong to poor family, are not able to complete their elementary level of education because their parents force them into the working sector in order to supplement their family income, usually when their age is in between ten to fifteen. Major objectives of the study explored the socio-economic and educational problems of dropout child labour in Kolkata. And the findings analyzed the different causes of school dropout of child labour at elementary level of education and also analyzed their present livelihood condition of the child labour.

Keywords : Elementary Level of Education, Dropout Child Labour.

Introduction

Child labour refers to children who miss their childhood and are not able to have the basic amenities which a child should have. The problem of child labour is huge and is faced by many countries in the world. It becomes a challenge and long-term goal for many countries to abolish all forms of child labour. Especially in developing countries, it is considered as a serious issue these days. Recently the International Labour Organization (ILO, 2013) estimated

there are around 215 million children between the ages five to seventeen who work worldwide. They are often mistreated and work for prolonged hours in very bad conditions. This can affect their health physically, mentally and emotionally. These children do not have the basic access to school or health care.

Children of course constitute wealth, but if they are too many, this wealth stinks. And this is exactly what is happening in developing countries, including India. Like all other

developing nations, in India many children who belong to poor family are not able to complete their elementary level of education because their parents force them into the working sector in order to supplement their family income. Usually between the age of ten to fifteen children are forced by the degree of fate to put in their labour in factories, hotels, restaurants, tea stalls, juice bars, road side motor garage and other eating places of Kolkata city in exchange of a few coins or simply for two meals. The working condition and environment of the child labour in urban area were quite horrible. Exploitation of child labour is reflected in terms of long hours of working at a relatively low wages, casual nature of work, absence of holidays, absence of social security etc. On the other hand poverty, parent's negligence and indifference in education, shortage of dwelling house and comfort and equipment and defective supervision and administration in the field of education keep them unskilled or semi-skilled which restrict the opportunities of vertical mobility.

Emergence of the Study

Child labour is a Universal phenomena and it is a by-product of socio-economic structure of the society. Child labour can be classified as hazardous and non-hazardous labours. Many poor parents procreate children in order to enhance family income and poverty forces child to drop out of school and find employment in order to supplement their family income.

Non-schooling of children has intimately connected with exploitation of child labour which is the consequence of social inequality, attitude of the privileged classes and lack of public involvement in the protection of basic entitlement. Lack of parental motivation and high

opportunity cost of schooling also contribute to aggravation of the problems of child labour.

According to Census, 2011, 1 in 4 children of school-going age is out of school in our country and 99 million children in total has dropped out from school in which 10.13 million are child labours between 5-14 years and 33 million are working children between the ages of 5-18 years (Census 2011). In the last decade of population census (2001 – 2011) we have also seen that the number of child labour has decreased in rural areas from 11.3 million to 8.1 million whereas in urban areas the number of child labour has increased from 1.3 million to 2.0 million. Kolkata is not the exceptional urban area in increasing child labour in organized and unorganized sectors. The Kolkata city is fastest growing city in India, especially in education, industries and hotel establishments. Specially in industries and hotel sectors the demand of labour force is huge. To meet this needs of labour force, owners of those working sectors choose child labour which is available in cheap than adult workers and engaged them into unhealthy, uncomfortable and harmful working condition.

In this article we describe and examine the conditions of educational status, working condition, and reasons for which child labours are being dropout from school and forced into different working sectors of Kolkata in spite of having different legislations made by Government and make some suggestions about how to eradicate this problem.

Objectives of the Study

1. To find out the reasons of school dropout of child workers.
2. To explore the educational status of child workers.

3. To explore the present livelihood condition of the child workers in their working sector.
4. To focus on their earning level.
5. To suggest some recommendations that would solve their problems in future.

Research Questions

1. Why children are left from school and engaged into the working sector as child labour?
2. What is the level of education of child workers?
3. What is the nature of present livelihood condition of the child workers in the unorganized sector?
4. What is the level of income of child workers?
5. How would the socio-economic and educational problem of child labour be solved?

Methodology

The purpose of this study is to analyze the educational status, present situation and various reasons of school dropout, which is being the problem of the child laborers engaged in unorganized sectors of Kolkata city. A case study research has been conducted for this purpose. At first we adopted Purposive Random sampling techniques to choose 50 dropout child workers from different unorganized sectors in Kolkata under the age of 16 years. Feedback from child workers

will be collected through interview and semi-structured questionnaire which will be carefully reviewed by use of suitable and sophisticated statistical techniques to represent. The questions were sometimes be true/false, multiple choice, and free response. Surveys included both open and closed ended questions. Collected and reviewed data are then described, analyzed and interpreted by quantitative and qualitative approach.

Analysis and Findings

Following are the findings based on the objectives of the study referring from the sources of Primary and Secondary data.

Table 1 : Reasons of school dropout

Reasons of Dropout	Kolkata	
	Number of Respondents (Under 50)	Percentage of Respondents
Poor economic condition	48	96
Migration of parents	4	8
Broken families	8	16
Less interest of education	22	44
Influenced by neighbors	9	18
Less interest of parents	17	34
Lack of school facilities	4	8

Poor economic condition

Majority of child labour (96%) of Kolkata were dropped out at elementary level without completing their elementary education due to poor economic condition of their family which forced them to be engaged in the working sectors for support of their family. Hence, here we found poverty as primary reason and migration of parents, broken family, less interest in Education, influenced by neighbors, less Interest of parents to Education and lack of School Facilities as secondary reasons of dropout besides of poverty.

Migration of parents

Migration of parents is another reason of school dropout of the child labour. Some respondents' parents left their native place and went to another place for employment or for business purpose with the family member. For this children were compelled to leave the school and move to the new place and some of them got readmission to new school but maximum left dropout. Even those who took admission they were also left school being unadoptable with the new situation without completing the elementary level of education. Due to this reasons 8% child labour of Kolkata were found drop out at elementary level.

Broken families

16 percent of the total respondents belonged to broken families. It means such respondents' parents had family problems. We found that due to father's death or father's addiction and frequent quarrels between mother and father motivated them in accepting employment. Under this circumstance children lived with mother under poverty and discontinued their school education to find employment.

Less Interest in Education

In this statement 44 percent of total respondents are showing less interest in their education. They are unaware about the importance of education; therefore children are more attracted towards employment than schooling. Some respondents have left the school for psychological reasons, i.e., fear of hard subject like mathematics and English, fear of examination, fear of teacher etc. In the present study we have found 44 % child labour of Kolkata.

Influenced by Neighbor

In this study we found 14% of child labours were influenced by their neighbor like friends or relatives to engage into the working sector for earning money by leaving the school education. Some of them said that their parents told them "what will you do with education? Otherwise if you engage into the working sector you will earn more money".

Less Interest of Parents to Education

We found that 34% child labours were engaged into the working sector without completing the primary education according to their parent's choice. Some of the reasons like poor economic condition and low socioeconomic status, parents of the respondents forced them to join into the working sector.

Lack of School Facilities

We found that lack of school facilities was an important cause besides of poverty for their dropout from school. Majority of child labours were came from rural areas of Howrah, Hoogly, South 24 Parganas and Medinipur. They said that due to absence of any nearest school they had to travel long distance to reach the school

which decreased their level of interest on studying in school and consequently they dropped out from the school. For this reasons 8% of child workers of Kolkata discontinued their elementary education.

Educational Status

Table: 2 Educational level

Educational Level	Respondents of Kolkata	
	Number	Percentage
Below class 3	13	26
Class 3 to 4	8	16
Class 4 to 5	9	18
Class 5 to 6	7	14
Class 6 to 7	6	12
Class 7 to 8	7	14
	50	100

From the above table we found that some of the child labours were left their school education before completing lower primary level and some of them before completing upper primary level of school education. We found majorities (60%) of surveyed child labours were dropped out at

lower primary level who were found to be working in the hotels, hosiery, garage, shops etc. And left 40% were dropped out from upper primary level who were found to be working in hosiery and hotel sector.

Physical and verbal torture

Table 3 : Percentage of Child Labour who faced different types of torture in their working sector:

Health Problems	Respondents of Kolkata	
	Number	Percentage
Physical torture	0	0
Verbal torture	28	56
Physical and Verbal torture	6	12
No torture	16	32

Physical and verbal torture on child labour is very common in every working sectors of Kolkata and. It's found that most of the surveyed child labours (56%) have experienced verbal torture in their working sectors, majority of them are working in hosiery and hotel sectors. 12% child labours have experienced both physical and verbal torture, they were found in garages and hotels and 32% child labour have said they didn't experience any kind of torture at their working

place, but after observation of real situation, it can be said that maximum number of child labour found working in hotels, hosiery, shops and garages were victims of both verbal and physical torture.

Working Hour

Table 4 : Different lengths of working hour of child labour

Working Hours	Respondents of Kolkata	
	Number	Percentage
Below 6	7	14
6 to 8	10	20
8 to 10	14	28
10 to 12	16	32
More than 12	3	6

Child labours are generally non-violent in nature. That’s why they have been exploited at their working sector in terms of long working duration. Majority of surveyed child labour (66%) who were working in Hotels and Hosiery sector have been working more than 8 hours. And left 34% child labours working in shop and garages have works less than 8 hours due to have fixed timing of work.

Level of Earning

Table 5 : Percentage of Child Labour in Different Income Level

Monthly income (in R.s)	Respondents of Kolkata	
	Number	Percentage (out of 50)
Below 2000	12	24
2000-4000	27	54
4000-6000	8	16
6000-8000	3	6
Total	50	100

Child labours are available as very cheap than adult workers. Because of this, most owners of the working sectors want to maximize their profit by paying as low salary to their workers. We found that 78% of surveyed child labour who are working in hosiery, hotel, shop, food factories, garage and mobile repairing centers have earned below 4000 rupees salary per month. Some of the total surveyed child labour (22%) who have engaged into the working sectors for more than 2 years and doing embroidering work in hosiery sector have earned 4000 to 8000 rupees salary per month.

Conclusion and Recommendations

It is to be noted that in spite of having various governmental schemes and interventions of NGO's, number of child labour still persistent in the urban areas who are being dropped out from school, enter into the different working sector in urban areas where they are exploited in many ways. So the educational and socio-economic problems of child labour are still present. It's like a cycle which starts from poor economic condition of family – parents compel to give more priorities on employment of their children than education - children dropout from school – they are engaged into the working sector - low level of income – again fall into poor economic condition. So here are some suggestions given below to compete with these problems:

1. More importance should be given on spreading of universal, free and compulsory education so that the parents do not have any difficulty or inconvenience to send their children to the school. The essential ancillary benefits like need of food and garments must also be covered under the arrangements. Regular administrative monitoring is necessary in this regard.
2. Government should activate a bottom-up approach in which first to prepare a district wise or block wise list of those families who are live under poor economic condition, and then initiatives of local NGOs and government officials have to visit those families and make conscious about the importance of education to those parents so that's in future they don't send their children for employment in childhood by dropping him out from school.
3. NGO's should have employed more workers in NCLP schools with the help of government to improve the follow up program, so that real underprivileged children can get scope of learning as well as no children leave the school without completing their elementary level of education.
4. It has been seen that with the help of NGOs many child labour has been returned to their normal life only in some areas where NGO's center or sub-center provide services for them. They should need to expand their services through establishing shelter home and NCLP schools with the help of Govt. at those places where child labour are found in present like Khiderpore area, Behala bazaar, Svabazar, Hatibagan area etc in Kolkata.
5. The government should provide free books, study materials, dress and increase the amount of stipend to those who are under BPL besides of mid day meal in NCLP schools.
6. Due to insufficient number of NCLP schools in comparison with the number of dropout child labour, the government should make a provision by which the normal schools will also manage an education system for child labour besides of NCLP schools.
7. The Government should take some remedial measures to remove poverty through increase the level of job opportunities and also help to implement plans and programs successfully.

References

- Agarwal, P.K., Dr. Pathak A.C. (2015). *A Socio-Economic Analysis of Child Labour India*. Journal of Science & Management (LJSM), Volume 1(Issue 1), 107-114.
- CRY.(2011). Statistics of children in India. Retrieve from <http://www.cry.org/statistics-on-children/>
- Debnath, B. (2016). Report on Child Labour in India. Retrieved from <https://blog.timetoswipe.com/2016-report-child-labour-in-india/>
- Mandal, S. (1993). Child Labour - With Special Reference to Calcutta. University of Calcutta, pp. 32 – 41.
- Rathod, G.R. and Koli, V.L. (2014). *Child Labour and School Dropout*. SRJIS, 3199-3206.
- Shandilya, T.K., Kumar, N. and Kumar, N. (2006). *Child Labour Eradication : Problems Awareness and Measures*. Deep and Deep Publications, New Delhi,
- Subhadarsani, S. (2014). *An Economic Perspective of Child Labour in Odisha: A Case Study of Rourkela*, National Institute of Technology, Rourkela, Odisha.
- UNICEF. Child labour in India statistics. Retrieved from <http://unicef.in/Whatwedo/21/Child-Labour>.

Received : 9th March, 2017

Accepted : 3rd July, 2017